

PLASMA-ASSISTED COMBUSTION FOR ENERGY INTENSE INDUSTRY

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The effective decarbonisation of the entire glass sector as soon as possible requires the development of new methods and technologies and the search for environmentally friendly alternatives to natural gas as a carbon-neutral alternative fuel. This paper presents the vision and latest results of the Horizon Europe project GIFFT (Sustainable Glass Industry with Fuel-Flexible Technology), whose overall objective is to develop a sustainable, hybrid and biofuel-flexible heat generation technology and process that can be integrated into industrial glass production through the efficient use of plasma combustion and gasification systems.

The GIFFT process provides high flexibility in fuel use and more dynamic operation in response to changes in energy and fuel markets. By combining available surplus electricity with alternative fuels such as hydrogen and biomass-derived syngas in a plasma combustion mode, up to half of the heat can be recovered from the electricity in the form of flame. This significantly extends the possibilities for achieving higher electrification of the process and, thus, lower CO₂ emissions. Preliminary results of combustion tests will be made available to demonstrate the validity of the theoretical assessment. This work evaluates the effect on the flame geometry by varying the fuel inlet parameters and the plasma-forming gases. In the present case, hydrogen is taken as an alternative gas for substituting natural gas. The oxidiser is pure oxygen. The flame geometry formed by the plasma-assisted burner is compared with the original methane-oxygen and hydrogen-oxygen combustion cases.

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